

From the above discussion it can be concluded that the ligand molecule coordinates with metal ions through two N atoms of oxime groups. Copper and Nickel ions form essentially square planar complexes with respect to the coordinating atoms, Co(II) ion has tetragonally distorted octahedral symmetry with water molecules occupying the axial positions and the nitrogen atoms in the equatorial plane.

The probable structures of the three metal complexes suggested on the basis of the experimental data are shown in Figs. 1-3.

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Electrolytic Reduction of Nitrogen to Ammonia

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Manuscript received 28 October 1975, accepted 6 January 1976

NITROGEN is extremely difficult to be reduced under mild conditions though there have been many recent attempts¹ to do so due evidently to its greater technological importance and enzymatic significance. In connection with our work on non-Faradaic electrolysis^{2,3} we have been considering the idea of electrons or H^- or $(H_2O)_a^-$ or similar reducing species being produced near the cathode and migrating towards the anode. We planned to test such a rather unconventional idea by noting whether nitrogen can be reduced near the cathode under conditions favourable to non-Faradaic electrolysis. We have achieved success and this preliminary note reports the same.

Experimental

The experimental arrangement is as shown in Fig. 1. We have chosen distilled water as the electrolyte as this is highly non-Faradaic in current conduction. As a precaution against spurious introduction of electrolytes which may act unfavourably the cellophane is freed of all electrolytes by repeated

washing with refluxing hot distilled water for days before use until the wash water shows no increase of conductivity. On sending a current of the order

Fig. 1.

of 1 mA through this solution for a few hours (preferably overnight), water in the cathode compartment turns deep pink to phenolphthalein. This unmistakably points out that an alkaline substance has been produced in the cathode solution. This turned out to be a mixture of small concentrations of ammonia and caustic soda, the latter being obtained from the sodium ion present in the glass and/or in the cellophane. That this solution contains ammonia as the dissolved base is conclusively proved by the fact that it gives positive reaction with Nessler solution. The Nessler test becomes very strong (precipitation) if the neutralised catholyte is reduced by evaporation to a small volume before testing with Nessler reagent. It is further observed that if dilute sulphuric acid ($\sim N/1000$) is used as the electrolyte, higher yield of ammonia is obtained. That the ammonia is derived from the dissolved nitrogen is proved as follows. Highly purified water which is saturated by bubbling highly purified nitrogen yields ammonia as described above but if water from which the dissolved nitrogen has been boiled off is used in an oxygen atmosphere, no detectable ammonia is formed. It may be mentioned that if the enclosed electrode is the anode, the dissolved nitrogen gets oxidised to nitric acid; details will be published later.

Attempts are being made to scale up the fixation process and increase the yield with a view to effecting direct fixation of nitrogen on a large-scale electrolytically. Further work is in progress to determine the influence of various factors.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Sri Prithwis Kumar Bose for essential experimental assistance.

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